

The Effect Of Turkey's Kis Data On Bist-Participation, Kis, Dowjones And Spsk Data For The Years 2021- 2024: An Ardl Bounds Test

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Abstract

Today, Islamic finance seeks to deliver financial services in accordance with Islamic principles and practices. Sukuk plays a significant role in Islamic banking, which has been evolving since the 1970s. In recent years, sukuk has received a lot of attention in Turkey, thanks to the involvement of Islamic banks and sukuk issued in collaboration with the Ministry of Treasury and Finance, which is sponsored by the government. Sukuk is an interest-free investment vehicle that has become popular among investors in recent years. It is widely utilized in nations such as Turkey, England, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE to offer finance. The purpose of this research is to undertake an econometric analysis of the influence of KIS data in Turkey on Bist - Participation, Bist-30, Dow Jones, and SPSK data from 2021 to 2024 using the ARDL bounds test technique. The analysis examined daily data from 16 November 2021 to 14 June 2024. The number of observations is 545. The ARDL model findings revealed a statistically significant association between the dependent variable KIS and the other independent variables. In general, it indicates that the dependent variable has a considerable effect on the values of the independent variables. The high variance (r-squared) value indicates that the model has a strong explanatory power.

Keywords : Sukuk, Borsa Istanbul-30, ARDL Bounds Test, Gel Classification: C58, R15, C01

Introduction

In 1980, Islamic Finance developed new products that were valued in markets while adhering to Islamic halal and haram principles (ERSİN, 2018).

According to YARDIMCIOĞLU (2014), Islam outlaws behaviors such as interest and gambling, as well as questionable activities with no guarantees. This circumstance has resulted in the establishment of an interest-free banking system in Muslim nations. The public recognizes many participation fund utilization techniques such as murabaha and musharaka as extremely significant institutions where the interest-sensitive and Islamic-minded section want to assess their investments (TÜRKAN, 2022).

The Sukuk market has grown significantly in recent years, and it has become more important internationally as a prominent Islamic financial product. Sukuk is an Islamic financial instrument selected by people or entities sensitive to Islamic interest (İÇELLİOĞLU, 2019). Sukuk, as defined by the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions, are "certificates of equal value representing undivided shares in the ownership of tangible assets, usufruct rights and services, specific projects, or project assets." According to the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), the standard-bearer for the interest-free financial system, sukuk are certificates issued with equal value that grant ownership rights to existing goods, benefits, or assets that provide services (TKBB, 2020). Sukuk, like derivatives, may be purchased and sold in secondary markets, with fixed or variable returns. Rating agencies may assess sukuks since they are listed in structured marketplaces. Sukuk refers to the practice of pooling investors' resources in order to produce 'halal' income in conformity with Islamic law's principles and beliefs. Between 2013 and 2023, Turkey's Participation Banks issued a total of 428.1 billion Turkish liras, whereas the Ministry of Treasury and Finance issued 313.5 billion Turkish liras. Participation Banks issue around 25% more sukuk than the state does. The quantities of sukuk issued throughout the years will be detailed in the sections below.

The purpose of this research is to first offer basic information regarding sukuk, then provide tabular and graphical data on sukuk issuances made by both Participation Banks and the Ministry of Treasury and Finance in Turkey between 2013 and 2023, and finally conduct analyses based on the relevant data. Then, perform a literature study on the issue, including national and international papers. Then, using an ARDL bounds test approach, it will undertake an economic study of the influence of Turkey's KIS data on BIST - Participation, BIST-30, KIS, Dow Jones, and SPSK data from 2021 to 2024. The lack of a national publication utilizing these data in the literature emphasizes the necessity for such a research. The research was designed to address this vacuum in the literature and contribute to the advancement of knowledge. This research employed the E-Views 9 program and 545 observations from 2021 to 2024.

The fastest rising products in recent years are becoming more well recognized and employed in Islamic capital markets. Since the 2008 global financial crisis, the percentage of sukuk certificates in the Islamic finance industry has increased to 20% due to increased interest in sukuk issuances (Advisors, 2021). Chart 1 depicts the total global value of sukuk assets in billions of dollars for the 13-year period 2010-2022. According to the IIFM's 2023 study, the value of sukuk assets has more than quadrupled from 53 billion US dollars in 2010 to 182 billion US dollars in 2022. The amount of international sukuk increased between these times. This figure is predicted to reach 850 billion US dollars by 2024.

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Graph 1: Sukuk Issuance Volumes in the World (billion \$)

Source:(IIFM, 2023)

Table: 1

Sukuk Issuances in Turkey (TL) (2013-2023)

Years(million)	Participation Banks Sukuk Issuance Volumes	Ministry of Treasury and Finance Sukuk Issuance Volumes	Total
2013	150	3333	3483

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2014	586	3173	3759
2015	2600	3390	5990
2016	3400	6262	9662
2017	7200	4260	11460
2018	20500	7254	27754
2019	40500	7601	48101
2020	54100	37155	91255
2021	96900	11478	108378
2022	83900	88312	172212
2023	81200	120994	202194
Total	391036	293212	684248

Source: (TKBB, 2024)

Tabulated by the author

According to the statistics in Table 1, both treasury and participation bank sukuk issuances grew year after year between 2013 and 2023. The growth over the previous three years has been especially significant. The most significant cause for the current surge is the tax laws enacted in 2016 to favor sukuk. As a result, the sukuk volume of participating banks climbed from 3 million 400 thousand in 2016 to 7 million 200 thousand in 2017. Furthermore, the Committed Transactions Market, which began functioning in BIST (Borsa Istanbul) in 2018, has provided a distinct boost to the sukuk market. Similarly, participation banks boosted their sukuk issuances from 20 million 500 thousand in 2018 to 40 million 500 thousand in 2019. When the sukuk issuance volumes of the Ministry of Treasury and Finance are compared to the sukuk issuance volumes of Participation Banks, the sukuk issuance volumes of the Ministry of Treasury and Finance are slightly lower in total, but when the sukuk issuances of the Ministry of Treasury and Finance are evaluated for the period 2013 - 2023, they show that they have gained significant momentum. For example, in 2023, 120 million 994 thousand sukuk were issued, compared to 3 million 333 thousand in 2013. This is a roughly 400% gain.

Separate graphical versions of Table 1 are shown below under the titles Graph 2 and Graph 3:

Graph 2

Participation Banks Sukuk Issuance Volumes Between 2013-2023 (Million TL)

Source: TKBB

Graphically rendered by the author .

According to Chart 2, Participation Banks' sukuk issuances grew practically every year between 2013 and 2023. The sukuk volume climbed from 150 million in 2013 to 96.9 billion in 2021. The small declining trend in recent years is due to the detrimental effect of the worldwide Covid-19 outbreak on the economy in 2020. Although it had a little downward trend in 2022 and 2023, it is deemed an increase since it did not dip below negative (-). It returned to its previous pattern within two years after the outbreak. The significant increase in Participation Banks' sukuk volumes demonstrates our country's success in this field.

Graph 3

Ministry of Treasury and Finance Sukuk Issuance Volumes in 2013-2023
(Million TL)

Source: TKBB

Graphically illustrated by the author.

Chart 3 illustrates that the Ministry of Treasury and Finance's sukuk issuance volumes climbed substantially from 2013 to 2023. The growth after 2019 is especially notable. While there was a large growth between 2019 and 2020, there was a pause after 2020. Unfortunately, the worldwide Covid-19 epidemic had a detrimental influence on the economy in 2020, although as seen in Figure 3, it began to increase again after 2020. While it was 11 million 478 thousand TL in 2021, it was 88 million 312 thousand by 2022. This is an increase of almost 800%. The related graphic shows an even larger growth from 2022 to 2024. We should expect an even larger growth in the next years.

1. Literature Review

Writer	Variable	Method	Findings Obtained
(MENSI, vd., 2024)	Sukuk and Islamic stock market in Asia, Europe and the World	Markov switching-vector autoregression and spread index models/ VAR model	It demonstrates that own shocks have a favorable effect on Islamic stock markets in low-income regimes. Under contrast, save for World assets, Islamic stock markets are unaffected by internal shocks under high volatility regimes. Sukuk is influenced by internal shocks in both molarity regimes, and this effect is amplified in high volatility regimes. Low volatility regimes have higher and lower persistence than high volatility regimes.
(GÜL, vd., 2017)	Interest rate – dividend – deposit relationship for participation banks in Turkey	Johansen cointegration method	It is discovered that there is a large linear link between the profit and interest rates. This link also has an impact on the participation instruments of the participation banks, leading to the conclusion that participation banks and classical banks have a mutual impact.
(KOÇAK, 2018)	Capital, labor and economic growth rates	Granger causality test based on	The causality test for economic growth sources demonstrates that Islamic finance,

	with Islamic finance	least squares and VECM	capital, and labor all have a unidirectional and positive effect on economic growth.
(MUSTAF A, vd., 2017)	Malaysian Islamic stock market with money supply, industrial production index, consumer price index and Islamic interbank interest rate	ARDL bounds testing and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)	The model includes Islamic macroeconomic variables, and there is a considerable long-term correlation between interbank interest rates and stock prices. Both monetary M2 and M3 sizes are positively correlated with stock prices. As a result, the liquidity effect propels the process forward.
(ALIM, vd., 2021)	Returns of Conventional and Islamic Portfolios	Simple OLS Regression	It demonstrates that sukuk returns are positive and substantial. Concurrently, traditional bonds have a decreasing trend, although long-term returns are large. Portfolio diversity should be sought in the marketplace.
(MATLOU THİ, BAHLOUL &, 2022)	Stock indices and Sukuk	Markov-variant Capital Asset Pricing Model	Islamic stock indexes cannot provide a safe haven during the crisis period for all chosen conventional markets. Sukuk, on the other hand, is a viable investment option in Brazil, Russia, and Malaysia. Except for Italy, the United States, and Spain, the Sukuk index offers very little

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			protection against significant conventional market falls.
(BOUKHA TEM, 2022)	Relationship between financial risk components and Saudi sukuk market	ARDL method	That exchange rate stability, foreign debt stability, and debt service stability are the primary drivers of SMD growth in Saudi Arabia, whereas international liquidity and current account stability play minor roles.
(DILBER, 2022)	Real GDP through sukuk issuance	Engle-Granger cointegration and Granger causality approaches	When the data from the causation link between the impacts of sukuk issuances by participation banks on economic development in Turkey are assessed, it is discovered that economic growth has a positive influence on sukuk issuance.
(PRIMAM BUDI, vd., 2023)	S&P GCC Bond Index S&P MENA Bond, S&P GCC Sukuk Index) and S&P MENA Sukuk Index	VAR extended common connectivity method	For starters, the Total Connectedness Index (TCI) of 73% suggests that the bond and sukuk markets in the GCC and MENA countries are very integrated. Second, the S&P MENA Bond Index and S&P MENA Sukuk Index are net forwarders, whilst the S&P GCC Bond Index and S&P GCC Sukuk Index are net purchasers.

(METOUI & GHORBEL, 2023)	Impact of Sukuk on economic growth	Generalized method of moments (GMM)	It demonstrates that the development of the Sukuk market has a considerable impact on economic growth, even after accounting for numerous metrics of financial market development and traditional causes of economic growth.
(ASL & RASHIDI, 2021)	Middle East and North Africa (MENA) stock index, sukuk and various securities indices	VAR (1) asymmetric Baba, Engle, Kraft and Kron multivariate Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (1,1) model	Volatility and asymmetric shock spillover between the sukuk index and the MENA stock market index, that is, the sukuk indices behave independently from the MENA stock market indices; however, shock and asymmetric shock spillover exist between the MENA stock indices and the bond indices, including conventional bonds.
(MUHARA M, vd., 2019)	The two-way relationship between the development of the Islamic stock and sukuk market	VAR model, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and Granger causality test	It was shown that there is a statistically significant positive association between sukuk assets and the financial performance of participating banks in the investigated nations.

	and economic growth		
(ŞENSOY, vd., 2020)	Bitcoin (BTC) vs. Dow Jones World Stock Market Index, regional Islamic stock exchanges and Sukuk markets	Var based wavelet model	Portfolio diversification using Bitcoin and Islamic stocks/Sukuk/Titans 100 varies with time and frequency. Portfolio risk is greater at lower frequency (long term). Higher frequency are attributed to increased co-movements between Bitcoin and Islamic stock markets.
(BHUIYA N, vd., 2020)	Developed and emerging market bond and bill indices	There is a model	The inclusion of a sukuk index in each bond index may lower the portfolio's VaR by around 30 to 50 percent for all developed and developing market bond indexes.
(ALAM, vd., 2018)	Default features of Sukuks issued by corporate firms in Malaysia	There is a model	Despite the minimal secondary market trading of Sukuk, Var estimations were found to be quite consistent with credit rating agency ratings. The analysis demonstrated that Sukuk in Malaysia was no riskier than conventional bonds.

(LISTIYA NI, vd., 2023)	sovereign sukuk and government external public debt on Indonesia's economic growth	ARDL model	It demonstrates that the public foreign debt variable has a considerable negative impact on economic growth in the long term, but the government sukuk variable has no influence on economic development.
(SUHARTI , 2021)	The relationship between investment decisions on government bonds and sukuk and macroeconomic variables	ARDL model	Macroeconomic and political factors (inflation, currency rates, and interest rates) as well as financial markets (funding rates, deposit rates, volumes, and coupon rates) all have a significant impact on rational investment choices in government bonds and Sukuk.
(BALCILA R, vd., 2016)	Risk spillover effects between conventional and Islamic stock and bond markets	Markov regime- switching GARCH model	Asymmetric shocks from conventional equities and bonds to Islamic bonds (Sukuk) have been reported. Sukuk shows a distinct pattern in the propagation of global market shocks than developing market bonds.

<p>(SCLIP, vd., 2016)</p>	<p>Volatility behavior between Sukuk and international stock indices</p>	<p>Multivariate GARCH models with dynamic conditional correlation (DCC)</p>	<p>Correlations between sukuk and the US and European equities markets. It also discovered that the volatility connections between sukuk and regional market indexes were stronger during the financial crisis. Despite their reduced volatility when compared to equities, investors who diversify well will obtain considerable crossover.</p>
<p>(ARFAOUI, vd., 2022)</p>	<p>Asymmetric and dynamic linkages between Sukuk and Islamic conventional stocks</p>	<p>VARMA-AGARCH modeling approach</p>	<p>It demonstrates strong dynamic linkages between Islamic and traditional stock indexes. The calculated hedging efficacy indicates that include stocks in a comprehensive sukuk portfolio has no impact on variance but marginally decreases the risk-adjusted return omitting the DJIM GCC stock index during the whole study period.</p>
<p>(İLHAN, 2021)</p>	<p>Sukuk and 2-year public bonds, exchange rate and BIST100 performance rates</p>	<p>Performance measurements with Sharp Ratio, Information Ratio and Sortino Ratio metrics</p>	<p>The Sharpe and Sortino performance ratios acquired during the 2008 mortgage crisis and the subsequent two-year period demonstrate that these funds have become a safe haven against the risk of equities and interest rates.</p>

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(AL-KHAZALI, vd., 2014)	Relationship between Dow Jones Islamic indexes and conventional Islamic indexes	Stochastic dominance approach	Islamic indexes beat traditional indices throughout the current global financial crisis. As a result, Islamic investment beats conventional investment during an economic slump.
(NAIFER, vd., 2016)	The dependency structure between Islamic bond returns and national, regional and global stock market returns	Archimedes copula Models	The three nations' sukuk markets have no major or weak dependent on the results of the local, regional, faith, and worldwide stock markets. However, the reliance patterns between the nations' local sukuk returns and the volatility of the returns on other stock markets varied.
(GOLDLE WSKI, vd., 2013)	sukuk and conventional bond issuances	Case study methodology	<i>The stock market reacts neutrally to news of conventional bond issuances but unfavorably to announcements of sukuk issuances.</i> This conclusion is attributable to the high demand for Islamic investment certificates and the adverse selection process, which favors sukuk issuances by low-quality borrowers.

<p>(ÖNER, 2023)</p>	<p>affecting sukuk issuances include GDP, interest rate, inflation, foreign direct investments, exports, participation bank dividend rates and banking sector size.</p>	<p>Panel data method</p>	<p>While GDP, interest rates, exports, participation bank profit share rates, participation bank assets, the stock market, public spending, and the banking sector all have a positive impact on sukuk issuance, inflation and foreign direct investments have a negative impact. Separate analyses of each element influencing sukuk issuances will considerably contribute to a rise in sukuk issuances.</p>
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The literature review table above provides a quick summary of the authors, variables, model employed, and results. The literature study findings show that the ARDL and Var models are the most often utilized in national and international research on sukuk and other variables. In addition to these models, numerous investigations have been undertaken using various methodologies. In general, data on sukuk has been analyzed using numerous models for different years and nations. Because of discrepancies in the variables employed in the research, the grouping method's findings will be shared. Because sukuk research using econometric analytic techniques are scarce in our country, the literature review table consists mostly of overseas works.

(MENSI, vd., 2024), (ALIM, vd., 2021)...(MATLOUTHI, BAHLOUL &, 2022)(ASL & RASHIDI, 2021)(NAIFER, vd., 2016)(AL-KHAZALI, vd., 2014)(SCLIP, vd., 2016)

(BALCILAR, vd., 2016)(ARFAOUI, vd., 2022)(İLHAN, 2021)(ŞENSOY, vd., 2020)
(GOLDLEWSKI, vd., 2013) shows.

(GÜL, vd., 2017), (DİLBER, 2022)...(KOÇAK, 2018)(MUHARAM, vd., 2019)(ÖNER,
2023)(LISTIYANI, vd., 2023)(LISTIYANI, vd., 2023)

Data and Methodology

Dataset

Econometric examination of the influence of Turkey's KIS data between 2021 and 2024 on BIST - Participation, BIST-30, KIS, Dow Jones, and SPSK data using an ARDL bounds test approach; the study's data set comprises of daily data for these indexes. Investing.com provided data for the BIST-30 index, BIST-Participation, KIS, Dow Jones, and SPSK. Data will be evaluated daily between November 16, 2021 and June 14, 2024. The total number of observations is 572.

Methodology

Distributed Lag Autoregressive Model (ARDL)

M. Hashem Pesaran, Yongcheol Shin, and Richard J. Smith created the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model in 2001. Distributed lag autoregressive models (ARDL) comprise both the current and lagged values of the independent variables, as well as the lagged values of the dependent variable.

The general ARDL(p,q) model was formulated by Pesaran and Shin as follows;

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$$y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 t + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i y_{t-i} + \beta' x_t + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i x_{t-i} + \epsilon_t$$

$$\epsilon_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

$$\epsilon_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

The ARDL (Auto-regressive Distributed Lag) model is implemented in two steps. In the first step, the existence of long-term and short-term links between variables is examined by determining the presence of cointegration. The lag lengths are determined using AIC (Akaike Schwartz Criteria) or SHC (Schwartz) selection criteria for dependent and independent variables, respectively. The model's lag length is the criteria with the shortest critical value among the lag lengths. The ARDL limits test allows for analysis without requiring variables to be stationary at the same level. Furthermore, this technique allows variables to be included in the analysis regardless of whether they are stationary at the level, at the initial difference, or both. The ARDL technique takes into consideration the appropriate lag levels of variables at various levels, while other tests do not. In the second step, the ARDL model is used to calculate long-term coefficients and standard errors. The model is computed for the long-term connection, and its coefficients are interpreted. The information about the data to be utilized in the analysis is shown below, followed by tables containing the transformation and abbreviations of the data included in the study.

Table 2		
Information About Data Used in the Application		
Name of the data	Description of data	Source of data
BIST-30	Stock performance of the 30 firms with the biggest	Investing.com

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	market value trading on Borsa Istanbul.	
BIST-PARTICIPATION	Performance of shares traded on the Borsa Istanbul suited for participation banking.	Investing.com
WINTER	The Qinvest Portfolio Lease Certificate Participation (FX) Fund	Investing.com
DOW JONES	Dow Jones Industrial Average.	Investing.com
SPSK	SP Fund Dow Jones Global Sukuk ETF stocks	Investing.com

Table 3	
Transformations Applied to Data Considered in Analysis and Their Abbreviations in Analysis	
Name of the Data	Abbreviation of Data

Logarithmic transformation of BIST-30 data	LNBIST30
Logarithmic transformation of BIST-KATILIM data	LNBIST PARTICIPATION
Logarithmic transformation of KIS data	LNKIS
Logarithmic transformation of SPSK data	LNSPSK

3. Analysis and Findings

3.1 Unit Root Test Results

The data in the table represents unit root testing (PP and ADF). These tests are used to assess the stationarity of time series. The PP and ADF test results for the variables under consideration are shown in tabular form below. Table 4 shows the unit root test results according to Philips Perron (PP).

Table:4						
PP Unit Root Test						
	At the level	LNKIS	LNBIST30	INDOW JONES	LNSPSK	LNBIST PARTICIPATION

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still	t statistic	-85,807	0.0871	-46,368	-61,597	-83,030
	Probability d.	0.0000	0.9646	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
		***	n0	***	***	***
fixed and trending	t statistic	-92,713	-24,826	-52,231	-62,364	-90,294
	probability d.	0.0000	0.3367	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000
		***	n0	***	***	***
stable and non- trending	t statistic	-0.7693	-33,156	-18,959	-32,189	-0.5581
	probability d.	0.3828	0.0009	0.0554	0.0013	0.4753
		n0	***	*	***	n0
	1.In the Difference					

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		d (LNKIS)	d (LNBIST30)	d (LNDOWJONES)	d (LNPSK)	d (LNBIST PARTICIPATION)
still	t statistic	-257,537	-256,902	-269,749	-247,240	-252,438
	probability d.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***	***	***	***
fixed and trending	t statistic	-257,343	-256,859	-277,813	-249,968	-252,245
	probability d.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***	***	***	***
stable and non- trending	t statistic	-257,717	-253,139	-266,902	-239,516	-252,645
	probability d.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***	***	***	***

(*) Significant at the 10% level; (**) Significant at the 5% level; (***) Significant at the 1% level; and (n0) Not significant.

Because the probability values for LNBIST30 series with constant level and trend are more than 0.05, it is clear that these series are not stationary in terms of level. In other words, this series is not stagnant, but rather has a constant and trend. With steady and non-trending The probability values for the LNKIS, LNBISTKATILIM, and LNDOWJINES series are larger than 0.05, indicating that these series are stationary at the level. However, in the PP test, in the first difference The t statistic values for all series are very low, and the probability values are less than 0.05. That is, following the initial difference operation, all series converge to I(0).

Table 5 shows the results of unit root tests using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test.

Table 5:						
ADF Unit Root Test						
	At the level					
		LNKIS	LNBIST30	INDOW JONES	LNSPSK	LNBIST PARTICIPATION
still	t statistic	-19,617	0.0807	-48,204	-70,299	-14,868

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	probability d.	0.3040	0.9641	0.0001	0.0000	0.5399
		n0	n0	***	***	n0
fixed and trending	t statistic	-35.383	-24,598	-54,487	-71,840	-31,636
	probability d.	0.0362	0.3483	0.0000	0.0000	0.0928
		**	n0	***	***	*
stable and non-trending	t statistic	0.8462	-32,974	-18,025	-19,055	-0.9413
	probability d.	0.8930	0.0010	0.0680	0.0543	0.3088
		n0	***	*	*	n0
	1. In the Difference					
		d (LNKIS)	d (LNBIST30)	d (LNDOWJONES)	d (LNSPSK)	d (LNBIST PARTICIPATION)

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still	t statistic	- 208,88 1	-118,526	-67,055	-70,627	-202,189
	probability d.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***	***	***	***
fixed and trending	t statistic	- 208,70 5	-118,679	-67.335	-71,603	-202,098
	probability d.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***	***	***	***
stable and non-trending	t statistic	- 208,28 1	-114,024	-155,794	-69,714	-201,718
	probability d.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***	***	***	***

Note: (*) Significant at the 10% level; (**) Significant at the 5% level; and (***) Significant at the 1% level. And (n0) is not significant.

With a steady level in ADF Test The probability values for the LKIS, LNBISTKATILIM, and LNBIST30 series are more than 0.05, indicating that they are not level stationary. **The probability values for the fixed and trendless LNBIST30, LNKIS, LNBISTKATILIM, and LNSPSK series are more than 0.05**, indicating that they are not stationary at the 5% statistical significance level. However, since the probability values for all series are smaller than 0.05 in the first difference, all series become stationary I(0) following the first difference procedure. In general, the PP and ADF test findings show that, although all series have stationary I(0), their stationarity in terms of level differs. Because the variables are stationary in diverse conditions, they will be evaluated using the ARDL approach.

Table 6				
Estimation Statistics of ARDL (3, 2, 1, 4, 0) Model				
Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	Tstatistics	Probability value
LNKIS(-1)	0.426462	0.038812	1,098,797	0.0000
LNKIS(-2)	0.113929	0.035425	3,216,022	0.0014
LNKIS(-3)	0.095817	0.030856	3,105,254	0.0020

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LNPSK	-1,361,251	0.213768	-6,367,899	0.0000
LNPSK(-1)	1,080,075	0.208986	5,168,172	0.0000
INDOW JONES	-0.522686	0.189947	-2,751,741	0.0061
INDOWJONES(-1)	0.133101	0.242441	0.549001	0.5832
INDOWJONES(-2)	0.559914	0.189587	2,953,340	0.0033
LNBIST PARTICIPATION	0.110969	0.017728	6,259,519	0.0000
LNBISTPARTICIPATIO N(-1)	0.302281	0.023075	1,310,013	0.0000
LNBISTPARTICIPATIO N(-2)	-0.151196	0.023856	-6,338,001	0.0000
LNBISTPARTICIPATIO N(-3)	-0.052850	0.019941	-2,650,343	0.0083
LNBISTPARTICIPATIO N(-4)	-0.042558	0.014467	-2,941,788	0.0034
LNBIST30	0.010509	0.010305	1,019,862	0.3083

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C	-3,393,118	1,123,507	-3,020,114	0.0026
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According to the results in Table 6, the dependent variable is LNKIS, the independent variables are LNBISTKATILIM, LNDOWJONES, LNBIST30, and LNPSK with a maximum lag of 8, according to the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and the method is ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag). The analysis is based on 545 observations, and the most appropriate model is ARDL (3, 2, 1, 4, 0). LNKIS(-1) equals 0.42. In other words, a one-unit rise in LNKIS in the previous period results in a 0.42-unit increase in LNKIS in the current period, which is not a very large amount but indicates a substantial link since the probability value is 0.00. LNBIST30 and LNDOWJONES are not significant since they exceed 0.05 at the 5% significance threshold in the first lag. Except for the LNBIST30 and Lndowjones(-1) data, the probability values for each series in the model with LNKIS as the dependent variable are statistically lower than 0.05 at the 5% significance level, indicating that they are significant. The model was found to be significant in the majority of series. Furthermore, the model's variance (r-square) of 0.91 indicates that it has a good explanatory power.

Table 7				
Bounds Test Results (F-Statistic Value Comparison Table)				
F Statistics	Critical Values at 1% Significance Level	Critical Values at 2.5% Significance Level	Critical Values at 5% Significance Level	Critical Values at 10% Significance Level

	Lower limit	Upper limit	Lower limit	Upper limit	Lower limit	Upper limit	Lower limit	Upper limit
15.84	3.74	5.06	3.25	4.49	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52

Table 7 illustrates the F statistic value derived from the Bounds Test applied to the ARDL (3, 2, 1, 4, 0) model, as well as the upper and lower critical values estimated for 1%, 2.5%, 5%, and 10% respectively. To be considered significant, the F statistic value derived from this analysis should be greater than the computed critical values. In this regard, the f statistic value of 15.84 derived from the ARDL (3, 2, 1, 4, 0) model, with the KIS Index as the dependent variable, is regarded noteworthy since it exceeds the critical values, implying long-term associations. This finding indicates a long-term correlation between the KIS index and the BIST30, BISTKATILIM, SPSK, and DOWJONES indices.

Table 8				
Long Term Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-statistic	Probability value
D(LNKIS(-1))	-0.209746	0.041723	-5,027,143	0.0000
D(LNKIS(-2))	-0.095817	0.030856	-3,105,254	0.0020

D(LNSPSK)	-1,361,251	0.213768	-6,367,899	0.0000
D(LNDOWJONES)	-0.522686	0.189947	-2,751,741	0.0061
D(LNDOWJONES(-1))	-0.559914	0.189587	-2,953,340	0.0033
D(LNBISTPARTICIPATION)	0.110969	0.017728	6,259,519	0.0000
D(LNBISTPARTICIPATION(-1))	0.151196	0.023856	6,338,001	0.0000
D(LNBISTPARTICIPATION(-2))	0.052850	0.019941	2,650,343	0.0083
D(LNBISTPARTICIPATION(-3))	0.042558	0.014467	2,941,788	0.0034
D(LNBIST30)	0.010509	0.010305	1,019,862	0.3083
CointEq(-1)	-0.363793	0.044120	-8,245,557	0.0000

Table 8 displays the Ardl model's long-term coefficients in the model with KIS as the dependent variable and BIST-Participation, BIST-30, Dow Jones, and SPSK variables as independent. The impacts of different variables in the model throughout time have been assessed, as well as their statistical significance. When the long-term coefficients of the ARDL (3, 2, 1, 4, 0) model are investigated, it is discovered that all variables except the BIST-30 index are significant at the 5% level, and the KIS index has a positive

influence. Table 8 shows a positive and substantial link between the KIS index and BISTPARTICIPATION, DOWJONES, SPSK, and all of them with each delayed index.

Table 9			
Breusch-Godfrey Test			
F-statistic	0.153773	Significance F(8, 522)	0.9963
Observed R2	1.281366	Significance chi square(8)	0.9958

After obtaining the findings of the ARDL model, several verification studies were performed on the model. The first of these is whether the series exhibits autocorrelation. To guarantee the consistency of the analysis's conclusions, the series should not exhibit autocorrelation. Table 9 shows the findings of the Breusch-Godfrey test, which was done for this purpose. As shown in Table 9, the statistical results obtained indicate that there is no autocorrelation between the indices. A significance level greater than 5% indicates that the null hypothesis of autocorrelation is rejected.

Table 10

Jargue-Bera Test

The Jarque-Bera test is used to verify the normalcy assumption. This test determines if error terms are typically distributed. The Jarque-Bera test result is 2243.427, whereas the probability value is 0.00. The Jarque-Bera test has a probability value of less than 0.05 at the 5% level of statistical significance, indicating that the model is significant and adequate for normal distribution.

Table 11			
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch -Pagan- Godfrey			
F statistics	9.071790	F Probability value(14,530)	0.0000
Observed R2	105.3535	Chi square probability value (14)	0.0000
Scaled description SS	581.0983	Probability chi square (14)	0.0000

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The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test measures the inverse of heteroskedasticity. The coefficient value of this test is 105.3535, whereas the probability value is 0.00. Since the probability value is less than 0.05, the model is significant, and there is no difficulty with heteroskedasticity.

Table 12			
ARCH Heteroscedasticity Test (Ramsey (Reset Test)			
	Value	Df	Probability value
T statistics	5.606238	529	0.0000
F statistics	31.42991	(1,529)	0.0000

- The RESET test is used to assess if the estimated model has any specification or model setup errors. It is the second test used to assess heteroscedasticity. The test results show that the t statistic is 5.60 and the f statistic is 31.42. The probability value for each statistic is 0.00. It is deemed statistically significant at the 5% level. The ARCH test result obtained in the second phase indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity in the model.

Evaluation and Conclusion

Sukuk, also known as a lease certificate, is one of the instruments that has gained popularity in recent years. Sukuk (lease certificate), which is issued by both public and private corporations as well as participation banks, intends to offer funding to investors while also paying periodic returns in proportion to the sukuk rights provided by investors. It's also commonly utilized over the globe. This research presents the evolution of sukuk issued worldwide, particularly in Turkey, using tables and graphs based on current statistics. As seen in the graph in the first section of the research, the value of sukuk assets, which was 53 billion US dollars in 2010, has more than quadrupled and will reach 182 billion US dollars in 2022, according to the International Islamic Financial Market's (2023) report. This demonstrates a growing tendency in the amount of foreign sukuk during the years specified. According to data obtained from the Participation Banks Association of Turkey (TKBB) and presented in the first sections of the study, according to the table of sukuk issuances of both the treasury and participation banks between 2013-2023, the total sukuk issued by the Participation Banks and the Ministry of Treasury and Finance in 2013 was 3 million 483; while the sukuk issued in 2023 was 202 million 194. This represents a 5700% rise. This finding supports the projection that sukuk issuance will grow further in the next years.

The literature review table then covers the publications that comprise econometric analyses done using various variables and methodologies on sukuk and national, regional, or global stock market returns in many nations throughout the globe, including our own. The data suggest that there is evidence of substantial correlations between sukuk and developed-country stock markets, but the sukuk index of developing nations offers limited protection against major market drops.

The purpose of this research is to compare the data of KIS (Qinvest Portfolio Lease Certificate Participation (FX) Fund) with BIST-Participation (participation in banking-appropriate equities listed on Borsa Istanbul). The purpose of this research is to examine the impact of BIST-30 (the performance of the 30 stocks with the highest market value

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traded on Borsa Istanbul), DOW JONES (Dow Jones Stock Exchange Industrial Index), and SPSK (SP Fund Dow Jones Global Sukuk ETF stocks) on the ARDL (Auto Regressive Distribute Lag) model. The analysis examined daily data from 16 November 2021 to 14 June 2024. The number of observations is 545. First, unit root tests were used to do the study. Philips Perron The results of the (PP) and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) tests show that, although all series' initial differences are stable, their stationarity in terms of level differs. The ARDL model's findings show a statistically significant association between the dependent variable KIS and the independent factors. In general, it indicates that the dependent variable has a considerable effect on the values of the independent variables. Furthermore, when the long-term coefficients of the model resulting from the ARDL (3, 2, 1, 4, 0) model, with the KIS Index as the dependent variable, are examined, it is determined that all variables except the BIST-30 index are significant at a significance level of 5%, and the KIS index is positively affected. The R-squared (variance) value of 0.91 is likewise fairly high, showing that the dependent variable explains the dependent variable very well, implying a substantial association. Furthermore, the model's AIC score (-1.65) indicates that it is very reliable and fits well with the observed data.

According to this model's study, investors should concentrate their portfolio management on the growth of certain financial and economic indicators and continually review their influence on KIS. Furthermore, investors may utilize the model to make long-term and short-term investment choices, but each decision should be based on individual circumstances and risk tolerance. Investors should diversify their assets to reduce risk. For example, investors should monitor local and worldwide market events and analyze the influence of factors like the Dow Jones Index and SPSK. Investors should develop methods based on technical analysis and current data, and back them up with regression findings. Furthermore, portfolio managers should establish investing strategies that are appropriate for the risks they face.

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